

SMARANDACHE PSEUDO- IDEALS

W. B. Vasantha Kandasamy
Department of Mathematics
Indian Institute of Technology, Madras
Chennai - 600 036, India.
E- mail : vasantak@md3.vsnl.net.in

Abstract

In this paper we study the Smarandache pseudo-ideals of a Smarandache ring. We prove every ideal is a Smarandache pseudo-ideal in a Smarandache ring but every Smarandache pseudo-ideal in general is not an ideal. Further we show that every polynomial ring over a field and group rings FG of the group G over any field are Smarandache rings. We pose some interesting problems about them.

Keywords:

Smarandache pseudo-right ideal, Smarandache pseudo-left ideal, Smarandache pseudo-ideal.

Definition [1]: A Smarandache ring is defined to be a ring A such that a proper subset of A is a field (with respect to the same induced operations). Any proper subset we understand a set included in A , different from the empty set, from the unit element if any, and from A .

For more about Smarandache Ring and other algebraic concepts used in this paper please refer [1], [2], [3] and [4].

Definition 1 Let $(A, +, \bullet)$ be a Smarandache ring. B be a proper subset of A ($B \subset A$) which is a field. A nonempty subset S of A is said to be a Smarandache pseudo-right ideal of A related to B if

1. $(S, +)$ is an additive abelian group.
2. For $b \in B$ and $s \in S$, $s \bullet b \in S$.

On similar lines we define Smarandache pseudo-left ideal related to B . S is said to be a Smarandache pseudo-ideal (S -pseudo-ideal) related to B if S is both a Smarandache pseudo-right ideal and Smarandache pseudo-left ideal related to B .

Note: It is important and interesting to note that the phrase "related to B " is important for if the field B is changed to B' the same S may not in general be S -pseudo-ideal related to B' also. Thus the S -pseudo-ideals are different from usual ideal defined on a ring. Further we define S -pseudo-ideal only when the ring itself is a Smarandache ring. Otherwise we don't define them to be S -pseudo-ideal. Throughout this paper unless notified $F[x]$ or $R[x]$ will be polynomial of all degrees, $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Theorem 2 Let F be a field. $F[x]$ be a polynomial ring in the variable x . $F[x]$ is a Smarandache ring.

Proof: Clearly $F \subset F[x]$ is a field which is a proper subset of $F[x]$, so $F[x]$ is a Smarandache ring.

If F is a commutative ring then we have the following:

Theorem 3 Let $R[x]$ be a polynomial ring. R be a commutative ring. $R[x]$ is a Smarandache ring if and only if R is a Smarandache Ring.

Proof: If R is a Smarandache ring clearly there exists a proper subset S of R which is a field. So $R[x]$ is a Smarandache ring.

Conversely if $R[x]$ is a Smarandache ring we have $S \subset R$ such that S is a field. So R must be a Smarandache ring. Since $R[x] = \left\{ \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} r_i x^i \mid r_i \in R \right\}$. $R[x]$ cannot contain any polynomial which has inverse. Hence the claim.

Example 1: Let $Q[x]$ be the polynomial ring over the rationals. Clearly $Q[x]$ is a Smarandache ring. Consider $S = \langle n(x^2 + 1) \mid n \in Q \rangle$ is generated under '+'. Clearly $QS \subseteq S$ and $SQ \subseteq S$. So S is a S -pseudo-ideal of $Q[x]$ related to Q .

Theorem 4 Let R be any Smarandache ring. Any ideal of R is a S -pseudo-ideal of R related to some subfield of R but in general every S -pseudo-ideal of R need not be an ideal of R .

Proof: Given R is a Smarandache ring. So $\phi \neq B$, $B \subset R$ is a field. Now I is an ideal of R . So $IR \subseteq I$ and $RI \subseteq I$. Since $B \subset R$ we have $BI \subseteq I$ and $IB \subseteq I$. Hence I is a S -pseudo-ideal related to B .

To prove the converse, consider the Smarandache ring given in Example 1. S is a S -pseudo-ideal but S is not an ideal of $Q[x]$ as xS is not contained in S . Hence the claim.

Example 2: Let $\mathfrak{R}$ be the field of reals. $\mathfrak{R}[x]$ be the polynomial ring. Clearly $\mathfrak{R}[x]$ is a Smarandache ring. Now $Q \subset \mathfrak{R}[x]$ and $\mathfrak{R} \subset \mathfrak{R}[x]$ are fields contained in $\mathfrak{R}[x]$. Consider $S = \langle n(x^2 + 1) \mid n \in Q \rangle$ generated additively as a group. Now S is a S -pseudo-ideal relative to Q but S is not a S -pseudo-ideal related to $\mathfrak{R}$. Thus this leads us to the following result.

Theorem 5 Let R be a Smarandache ring. Suppose A and B are two subfields of R . S be a S -pseudo-ideal related to A . S need not in general be a S -pseudo-ideal related to B .

Proof: The example 2 is an illustration of the above theorem.

Based on these properties we propose the following problems:

Problem 1 Find conditions on the Smarandache ring so that a S-pseudo-ideal which are not ideals of the ring related with every field is a S-pseudo-ideal irrelevant of the field under consideration.

Problem 2 Find conditions on the Smarandache ring so that every S-pseudo-ideal is an ideal.

Example 3 $Z_{12} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, 11\}$ be the ring. Clearly Z_{12} is a Smarandache ring for $A = \{0, 4, 8\}$ is a field in Z_{12} with $4^2 = 4 \pmod{12}$ acting as the multiplicative identity. Now $S = \{0, 6\}$ is a S-pseudo-ideal related to A . But S is also an ideal of Z_{12} . Every ideal of Z_{12} is also a S-pseudo-ideal of Z_{12} related to A .

Problem 3 Find conditions on n for Z_n (n not a prime) to have all S-pseudo-ideals to be ideals.

Example 4 Let $M_{2 \times 2}$ be the set of all 2×2 matrices with entries from the prime field $Z_2 = \{0,1\}$.

$M_{2 \times 2} = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ be the ring of matrices under usual matrix addition and multiplication modulo 2.

Now $M_{2 \times 2}$ is a Smarandache ring for $A = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a field of $M_{2 \times 2}$. Let $S =$

$\left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$, S is a Smarandache pseudo-left ideal related to A but S is not a

Smarandache pseudo-right ideal related to A for $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ as $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \notin S$.

Now $B = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is also a field. $S = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a left ideal related

to B but not a right ideal related to B . $C = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a field. Clearly S is not a

Smarandache pseudo-left ideal with respect to C . But S is a Smarandache pseudo-right ideal with respect to C .

Thus from the above example we derive the following observation.

Observation: A set S can be a Smarandache pseudo-left ideal relative to more than one field. For $S = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a Smarandache pseudo-left ideal related to both A and B . The same set S is not a Smarandache pseudo-left ideal with respect to the related field $C = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ but S is a Smarandache pseudo-right ideal related to C .

Thus the same set S can be Smarandache pseudo left or right ideal depending on the related field. Clearly S is a S -pseudo-ideal related to the field $D = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$.

Definition 6 Let R be a Smarandache ring. I be a S -pseudo-ideal related to A , $A \subset R$ (A a field). I is said to be a Smarandache minimal pseudo-ideal of R if I_1 is another S -pseudo-ideal related to A and $(0) \subseteq I_1 \subseteq I$ implies $I_1 = I$ or $I_1 = (0)$.

Note: The minimality of the ideal may vary in general for different related fields.

Definition 7 Let R be a Smarandache ring. M is said to be a Smarandache maximal pseudo-ideal related to a subfield A , $A \subset R$ if M_1 is another S -pseudo-ideal related to A and if $M \subseteq M_1$ then $M = M_1$.

Definition 8 Let R be a Smarandache ring. A S -pseudo-ideal I related to a field A , $A \subset R$ is said to be a Smarandache cyclic pseudo-ideal related to a field A , if I can be generated by a single element.

Definition 9 Let R be a Smarandache ring. A S -pseudo-ideal I related to a field A , $A \subset R$ is said to be a Smarandache prime pseudo-ideal related to A if $x \bullet y \in I$ implies $x \in I$ or $y \in I$.

Example 5: Let $Z_2 = (0, 1)$ be the prime field of characteristic 2. $Z_2[x]$ be the polynomial ring of all polynomials of degree less than or equal to 3, that is $Z_2[x] = \{0, 1, x, x^2, x^3, 1+x, 1+x^2, 1+x^3, x+x^2, x+x^3, x^2+x^3, 1+x+x^3, 1+x+x^2, 1+x^2+x^3, x+x^2+x^3, 1+x+x^2+x^3\}$. Clearly $Z_2[x]$ is a Smarandache ring as it contains the field Z_2 .

$S = \{0, (1+x), (1+x^3), (x+x^3)\}$ is a S -pseudo-ideal related to Z_2 and not related to $Z_2[x]$.

Example 6: Let $Z_2 = (0,1)$ be the prime field of characteristic 2. $S_3 = \{1, p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, p_5\}$ be the symmetric group of degree 3. Here $1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$, $p_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$, $p_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, $p_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 1 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$, $p_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ and $p_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$. Z_2S_3 be the group ring of the group S_3 over Z_2 . Z_2S_3 is a Smarandache ring. $Z_2S_3 = \{1, p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, p_5, 1+p_1, 1+p_2, \dots, p_1+p_2+p_3+p_4+p_5, 1+p_1+p_2+p_3+p_4+p_5\}$. Now $A = \{0, p_4+p_5\}$ is a

field $A \subset Z_2S_3$. Let $S = \{0, 1 + p_1 + p_2 + p_3 + p_4 + p_5\}$ be the subset of Z_2S_3 . S is a S -pseudo-ideal related to A . S is also a S -pseudo-ideal related to Z_2 .

Theorem 10 Let F be a field and G be any group. The group ring FG is a Smarandache ring.

Proof: F is a field and G any group FG the group ring is a Smarandache ring for $F \subset FG$ is a field of the ring FG . Hence the claim.

Theorem 11 Let $Z_2 = \{0,1\}$ be the prime field of characteristic 2. G be a group of finite order say n . Then Z_2G has S -pseudo-ideals, which are ideals of Z_2G .

Proof: Take $Z_2 = \{0, 1\}$ as a field of Z_2G . Let $G = \{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{n-1}, 1\}$ be the set of all elements of G . Now $S = \{0, (1+g_1 + g_2 + \dots + g_{n-1})\}$ is a S -pseudo-ideal related to Z_2 and S is also an ideal of Z_2G . Hence the claim.

Problem 4 Find conditions on the group G and the ring R so that the group ring RG is a Smarandache ring?

References

- [1] Padilla, Raul. *Smarandache Algebraic Structures*, Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences, Delhi, Vol. 17 E., No. 1, 119-121, (1998)
<http://www.gallup.unm.edu/~smarandache/ALG-S-TXT.TXT>
- [2] W.B.Vasanth Kandasamy, *Obedient Ideals in a Finite Ring*, J. Inst. Math. & Comp. Sci., Vol. 8, 217 - 219, (1995).
- [3] W.B.Vasanth Kandasamy, *On ideally strong group rings*, The Mathematics Education, Vol. XXX, 71 - 72, (1996)
- [4] W.B.Vasanth Kandasamy, *On Generalized Semi-ideals of a Group Ring*, The Journal of Qufu Normal University., Vol. 18, No. 4, (1992).